

A Meta-Review of Strategic Human Resource Management

Wako Jio¹, Chalchissa Amentie Kero²

¹PhD Scholar, Department of Management, College of Business & Economics, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia.

²Associate Professor, Department of Management, Jimma University, Ethiopia.

Abstract – The field of strategic HRM has experienced substantial expansion in recent years. By doing a meta-review—a review of the reviews that have covered various aspects of strategic HRM—this article synthesizes the literature in this area. The authors also analyze current trends in the study of strategic HRM while highlighting conceptual frameworks and empirical results from studies conducted in the area over the previous three decades, pointing out methodological problems and difficulties in the earlier research. The author offers a meta-review of a few intriguing literature and significant directions for further research as a conclusion.

Keywords: Strategic HRM, Meta-review, Synthesis, Literature.

1. INTRODUCTION

As SHRs continue to play a significant role in modern organisations, strategic HRM has developed over the past 30 years into a unique subject of study. Strategic HRM scholarship, as defined by Almashyakhi (2022), is the "study of HRM systems (and/or subsystems) and their interrelationships with other elements constituting an organisational system, including the organization's external and internal environments, the multiple players who enact HRM systems, and the multiple stakeholders who evaluate the effectiveness of the organisation and determine its long-term survival" (p. 4). Jackson et al.'s definition, which distinguishes strategic HRM from conventional HRM research, emphasizes HRM systems and their relationships with other organizational components, such as organisational performance and effectiveness. This is consistent with other scholars' definitions (Verma et al., 2022).

Over the past couple decades, strategic HRM has drawn more and more attention from management researchers and practitioners. Strategic HRM literature has significantly grown since its inception in the 1980s, as depicted in Figure 1. From 1980 to 2016, the Scopus database lists approximately 8126 publications that contain the phrase "strategic human resource management." These papers, which were distributed in over 150 journals, involved academics from over 120 different nations. About 32,000 publications on the subject of strategic HRM are available in Google Scholar, and this number is growing quickly. In order to progress the field of strategic HRM, it is important to comprehend what has been done in the past and what can be done in the future. A thorough analysis of earlier studies in this field is essential.

A number of significant conceptual and meta-analytic reviews of strategic HRM have been published, including those by Kim et al., (2022); Verma et al., (2022); Almashyakhi (2022). However, as demonstrated in Figure 1, the area of strategic HRM has rapidly expanded during the past ten years, with 5896 out of 8216 total publications in the topic being published between 2007 and 2016. There is a need for an updated evaluation to address the major conclusions from earlier reviews as well as new trends and areas of recent empirical study. The current paper takes a focus on this purpose. Considering this goal in mind, the current research employs a "meta-review" methodology to compile the conclusions of earlier conceptual and empirical

strategic HRM review studies. Given the vast body of work in this field, the meta-review approach is a useful tool to comprehend the state of the strategic HRM paradigm. This method also goes beyond a conventional review by exposing the theoretical and methodological problems that permeate this discipline, providing a fundamental and thorough grasp of the current situation and the key difficulties it faces.

To identify the main theoretical frameworks used in strategic HRM research, summaries the main findings of empirical work, and discuss the key methodological issues (such as measurement issues and research design), we reviewed 68 reviews that have covered various theories and topics of strategic HRM. Additionally, when addressing specific points, we connect readers to examples of reviews. Furthermore, we examine 183 empirical studies on strategic HRM to supplement the meta-review. When analyzing the empirical studies, we pay close attention to how the research questions have evolved over time, highlighting in particular the recent decade's new trends. Finally, we talk about some fascinating and crucial issues for future research on strategic HRM.

2. REVIEWS ON STRATEGIC HRM

2.1 Search for prior reviews of strategic HRM

The terms "strategic human resource management" and "review" were searched for in academic articles and book chapters in the EBSCO Business Source Premier, Web of Science, and Scopus databases. The conceptual and meta-analytic reviews were included in this meta-review based on two criteria. First, we included papers whose main goal was to summarize and synthesize earlier research. We didn't include theoretical articles (such as Adula et al., (2023); Kim et al., (2022), Verma et al., (2022); Almashyakhi (2022) that were primarily concerned with formulating theoretical models and assertions. Second, we excluded articles about specific HRM practices (such as Yu, Yuan, Han, Li & Li (2022) and international HRM (such as Adula, Kant & Birbisa (2023)); instead, we included review articles about HRM systems and their relationships with other variables.

68 review articles about strategic HRM, including 64 conceptual reviews and 4 meta-analyses, were produced using these two criteria. Based on the theoretical framework/perspectives, methodological issues, and review articles' coverage of those topics, we classified conceptual reviews. The meta-analytic reviews were not coded, and the main conclusions from them are just briefly covered in the part that follows.

2.2 Theoretical Foundations of Strategic HRM

The central and defining research question in strategic HRM, according to Tufa & Kant (2023) is the connection between strategic HRM and organisational effectiveness. To explain why, how, and when HRM systems are connected to organisational outcomes, academics have used a variety of theories. More than 20 theories or theoretical perspectives were found after we coded the theories presented in earlier conceptual assessments (see Table 1). The resource-based view, human capital theory, the behavioural viewpoint, the ability-motivation-opportunity (AMO) framework, and social exchange theory are among the theories that have been often discussed in earlier reviews (at least in 10 articles).

Table -1: Summary of strategic HRM theories in prior reviews.

Resource-based view	37
Behavioral perspective	22

Human capital theory	20
AMO framework	14
Social exchange theory	10
Institutional theory	9
Agency/Transaction costs	8
Organizational climate	8
Resource dependence	7
Attribution theory	5
Social capital theory	3
General system theory	3
Cybernetic	2
Employee-organization relationship	2
Organizational learning theory	2
Psychological contract theory	2
Equity theory	2
Self-determination theory	1
Population ecology	1
Symbolic theory	1
Strategic reference points theory	1
Strategic agreement theory	1

Source: Researcher own Meta analysis, 2023

According to the resource-based view, enterprises might potentially derive sustainable competitive advantage from valuable, uncommon, unique, and non-substitutable resources (Barney, 1991; Wernerfelt, 1984). Based on this viewpoint, a number of academics have proposed theories explaining how HRs or HRM systems might satisfy the four requirements and, as a result, potentially serve as a source of long-term competitive advantage (Gobena & Kant (2022)). Many empirical studies use this theory to explain the beneficial association between HRM systems and organisational performance. These theoretical works have established the foundation for applying the resource-based view to strategic HRM research. Despite becoming a paradigm for strategic HRM research, the resource-based concept has recently come under fire. Negeri et al., (2023) pointed out that the four requirements for sustained competitive advantages have not been adequately investigated in terms of how HRM systems may produce employees who match these requirements.

Fig -1: SHRM Theories Numbers of times identified in prior reviews

Source: Researcher own Meta analysis, 2023

Human capital theory, which is similar to the resource-based view, views human capital as a firm-level resource that can improve business performance and produce economic value (Barney & Wright, 1998; Wright & McMahan, 2011). Human capital, in contrast to other resources, is held by employees and transferable to other businesses in the event that people depart. Therefore, it is essential for businesses to use HRM systems to both improve their current levels of human capital (for example, by recruiting and training staff) and prevent losing their human capital investments to rival businesses (for example, by motivating and retaining employees). Strategic HRM topics including the HR architecture (Negeri et al., 2023) and the connection between HRM systems and organisational performance have all been addressed using human capital theory.

The behavioural viewpoint emphasizes how HRM systems may help organisations accomplish their strategic goals, whereas the resource-based view and the human capital theory highlight the importance of HRs and HRM systems. The behavioural perspective, which has its roots in role theory, contends that in order to successfully navigate both internal and external environments, organisations must have the desired role behaviours of their workforce. By managing and reinforcing these desired behaviours, HRM systems can improve organisational effectiveness. Theoretically, the relationship between HRM systems and organisational outcomes can be examined by using the behavioural viewpoint to look at the mediating mechanisms. The behavioural approach is frequently used by researchers to pinpoint specific mediators and investigate how HRM systems impact employee behaviours, which in turn affect organisational effectiveness.

According to Yadete et al. (2014), the behavioural perspective is regarded to be a version of the AMO framework. According to this paradigm, an employee's ability, motivation, and opportunity to achieve are all related to their level of performance (Gerhart, 2007). By improving the three facets of employee performance, HRM systems can help a company perform better (Jiang et al., 2012a). The AMO framework has been extensively employed in strategic HRM research to describe the mediating processes through which HRM systems are related to organisational performance, similar to how the behavioural perspective has been used (e.g., Garuma, 2023). According to research, HRM systems can be separated into sub-dimensions based

on the AMO model, such as skill-enhancing, motivation-enhancing, and opportunity-enhancing HRM practises. Additionally, different HRM system components have an impact on firm performance.

Social exchange theory has been used more and more in strategic HRM research since there is growing interest in how HRM systems impact organisational performance by influencing employee attitudes and behaviours. Gouldner's (1960) reciprocity norm and Blau's (1964) study of social exchange connections serve as the foundation for social exchange theory. According to this hypothesis, those who gain advantages from one party often reciprocate. The organisation may view HRM systems designed to benefit employees as an investment in those individuals; in return, those individuals may show favourable attitudes and behaviours towards the organisation in order to preserve the exchange relationship. Theoretically, HRM systems can boost organisational performance by improving employees' social exchange relationships with organisations, according to research (Gile et al., 2022).

Prior review studies have also noted a number of additional theoretical views in addition to the theories summarised above, including institutional theory, organisational climate theory, social capital theory, and attribution theory (see Table 1). In the strategic HRM literature, each of these ideas has been applied to explain various research topics. For instance, institutional theory is useful for comprehending how organisations implement HRM systems based on the setting of a firm. Wright and McMahan (1992) contend that despite rational decision-making being based on an organization's strategic goals, the implementation of HRM systems may not necessarily be the end outcome of that process. Instead, the organisation may be forced to implement specific HRM practices as a result of internal and external circumstances in order to establish credibility.

In order to comprehend why different employees react in various ways to the same HRM systems, attribution theory has lately been incorporated into the strategic HRM literature. Employee attributions on the goal of putting HRM systems in place can affect their group behaviours and unit performance, according to Nishii, Lepak, and Schneider (2008). We are unable to fully introduce each of the hypotheses given in the Table due to the length of this review. We direct those who are interested in finding out more about these theories to the supplementary material and suggest that they read other reviews that place a stronger emphasis on the theoretical underpinnings of strategic HRM (Gile et al., 2022). Future studies may take into account some of the less often used.

2.3 Empirical Findings of Strategic HRM

We base our discussion of the empirical findings of strategic HRM on the four meta-analytic reviews that have been completed (Gile et al., 2022), even though the majority of conceptual reviews of strategic HRM have summarised the findings of empirical studies. The associations between HRM systems and organisational results were investigated in all four of the meta-analyses. In their groundbreaking meta-analysis of strategic HRM, Gile (2022) discovered beneficial connections between high-performance work systems (HPWSs) and organisational performance. They also looked at how the different types of industries and performance outcomes affect the primary impact of SHRM.

The findings of Solomon & Lemma (2022) emphasise the significance of grouping HRM practices into bundles intended to improve particular traits of human capital. Additionally, the moderating effects of national characteristics on the association between HPWSs and business performance were the main focus of Tufa & Kant (2023) research. They discovered that countries with a closely knit national culture that is more consistent with HPWSs (such as low power distance or high performance-orientation) also had a stronger

positive association between HPWSs and business performance. Their findings demonstrate how crucial national cultures are to comprehending the connection between HPWSs and corporate performance.

Solomon & Lemma (2022) looked at the mediating mechanisms of the association between HRM practices and financial performance, which was different from the previous three meta-analyses. They also used the AMO model to divide HRM practices into three different policy domains. They discovered that, compared to the motivation-enhancing and opportunity-enhancing HRM policy domains, the skill-enhancing HRM policy domain has a stronger relationship with human capital and a weaker relationship with employee motivation. This finding demonstrates how various approaches exist for HRM system elements to influence results. The discovery by Gile et al., (2022) that the two employee outcomes moderate the effects of HRM systems on organisations' operational and financial success is another contribution to the field.

When taken as a whole, the meta-analytic evaluations have revealed significant modifiers of this relationship across levels and have offered substantial evidence for the beneficial association between HRM systems and various organisational outcomes. They also offer some preliminary findings for the mediating processes of the association between HRM systems and performance outcomes. Although all of the meta-analytic studies to date have concentrated on the connection between HRM systems and performance outcomes, the meta-analyses also provide potential for future quantitative reviews. It's crucial to comprehend the variables, such as organisational traits and environmental circumstances, which affect how HRM systems are adopted in organisations.

Furthermore, such meta-analytic evaluations heavily relied on bivariate correlations between organisational results and HRM systems. As more studies become available that offer sufficient data from which partial correlations can be generated, future study can use partial correlation coefficients to confirm the results of prior meta-analyses. Meta-analyses based on partial correlations are more rigorous in their analysis of the relationship between HRM systems and organisational results than typical meta-analytic reviews because they may estimate the main association while controlling for other variables. Additionally, the qualitative review by Gile et al., (2022) discovered discrepancies in the findings of moderating effects, such as the moderating influence of company strategy. Future meta-analyses are required to thoroughly synthesize the moderating effects on the link between HRM systems and performance outcomes and to resolve the conflicting findings.

2.4 Methodological Issues of Strategic HRM

Numerous review articles have reviewed the theoretical underpinnings and empirical results of strategic HRM in addition to discussing methodological concerns. As shown in Table 2, we divided the frequently debated methodological difficulties into five categories: level of analysis, assessment of HRM systems and measurement of performance outcomes, research design, and missing data. Since measuring HRM systems has received the most attention from previous reviews and is strongly tied to other methodological concerns, we focus primarily on these topics in the current review. We advise researchers interested in additional methodological issues to consult numerous earlier reviews.

Table -2: Summary of methodological issues of strategic HRM in prior reviews.

Methodological issues Numbers of times identified in prior reviews	
Measurement of HRM systems	31

Measurement of performance outcomes	20
Level of analysis	16
Research design	15
Missing variables	5

Source: Researcher own Meta analysis, 2023

Although studies have come to the conclusion that HR systems are a collection of practises, there is much less agreement over the conceptualization and operationalization of these systems (Panigrahi et al., 2022). It is challenging to compile and compare the results of HRM systems from various studies due to the lack of agreement regarding HR system components. Previous reviews have covered a number of issues. Researchers must first acknowledge that there is no one HR system that can be used to handle all employee types in an organisation. Due to each type of employee's distinct contributions to organisational goals, several academics have proposed that organisations utilize various HR practices to manage them (Panigrahi et al., 2022).

Fig -2: Empirical review

Source: Researcher own Meta analysis, 2023

In such a scenario, it is crucial for strategic HRM researchers to outline the different employee categories that the HRM systems are intended to cover before creating specific practises to represent the systems. For instance, Solomon & Lemma (2022) concentrated on HRM systems for managing staff members who interact with customers. Solomon & Lemma (2022) looked at middle managers' use of HRM systems. Researchers can pick the best practises that relate to certain employees by concentrating on a particular job group of employees. Instead of describing HRM systems only by identifying a set of practices, this may offer more accurate information. Relatedly, the ways that HRM systems are used by organisations may differ based on those reasons. Collins and Clark (2003), for instance designed an HRM system designed to create the social network of senior management teams. In Solomon & Lemma (2022) suggested an HRM system for workplace safety. A HRM system was created by to improve customer happiness and service performance. According to

this school of thought, researchers must develop HRM systems for particular organisational aims and necessary role behaviours if they are to accurately conceptualize HRM.

Second, research must take into account which practises should be incorporated in the HRM system after identifying the scope and goal of the system. Hundreds of HRM practices have been utilized in past studies, according to reviews that have recently been published (Solomon & Lemma (2022)). The specific practices incorporated in HRM systems also differ significantly from study to study. Many academics have proposed using a theoretical framework to direct the choice of practices rather than picking practices at random from a long list of HRM practises. According to Boxall & Purcell (2008), Jiang et al. (2012)^a, and Lepak et al. (2006), the AMO model, for instance, offers a framework for academics to group various HRM practices into three bundles.

Third, in addition to choosing the level to measure the system at, researchers must also consider the major elements that make up an HRM system. The structural hierarchy found in HRM systems, such as the HRM philosophy, HRM policies, and HRM practices, is referred to as the "level" in this context (Schuler, 1992). HRM policies are defined as "the firm's or business unit's stated intentions about the kinds of HR programmes, processes, and techniques that should be carried out in the organisation" (Wright and Boswell, 2002, p. 263). It is possible to compare how people are managed across organisations by concentrating on HRM policies, regardless of the methods used to carry them out. Focusing on HRM rules, however, may result in erroneous HRM practices because policies cannot reflect the actual practices adopted in the organisations.

2.5 Recent Trends of strategic HRM

Additionally, we looked for empirical research that looked at the connections between HRM practises and performance results. By doing this, we hope to show how the area of strategic HRM has changed since its inception and to point out some trends that have emerged in the last ten years. Since this is congruent with the notion of strategic HRM scholarship (Jackson et al., 2014), we restricted our search to works that examined HRM systems at the unit level of analysis. However, we also included articles looking at outcomes at the individual and unit levels. A final sample of 183 empirical studies was obtained through the principal databases' searches (such as EBSCO and Web of Science).

Fig -3: number of studies research analysis type
Source: Researcher own Meta analysis, 2023

Levels of analysis, research models, and research designs were the three categories we used to code the empirical publications. First, the levels of analysis show whether a study looks at connections between HRM systems and results at a single level (such as businesses and enterprises) or across levels. The unit-level analysis has dominated strategic HRM research for the past 20 years, as illustrated in Figure 2, as a result of academics' dedication to proving the impact of HRM systems on organisational results. However, since the late 2010s, academics have been more interested in multilevel research in the field of strategic HRM. The development of multilevel methodology and researchers' interest in comprehending employees' views of and responses to HRM systems have fueled interest in this multilevel approach.

Second, we classified whether an empirical study assessed the main impact of HRM systems on outcomes, included a moderation test, a mediation test, or neither. Figure 3 illustrates how many studies in the early stages of strategic HRM research concentrated on the primary impact of HRM systems. However, by looking at the moderators and mediation processes of the relationship between HRM systems and performance outcomes in organisations, researchers have considerably expanded the field of strategic HRM research. Jackson and colleagues (2014) have provided a thorough analysis of the moderators and mediators looked at in earlier studies.

Third, we categorized whether an empirical study employed a longitudinal, time-lagged, or cross-sectional design. A time-lagged design refers to collecting performance outcomes data after HRM systems data has been collected, whereas a cross-sectional design refers to gathering data on both at the same time. A longitudinal design is distinct from these two in that it involves gathering repeated measurements of HRM systems and performance outcomes over time. As can be seen in Figure 4, our coding findings agree with (Gile et al., 2022) assertion that cross-sectional designs have been used in the majority of strategic HRM research.

Fig -4: Measurement method Meta analysis

Yet, over the past ten years in particular, the number of research adopting a time-lagged design has gradually increased. More recently, researchers have begun to look at the long-term effects of HRM systems or the effects of changes to HRM systems on performance outcomes (Gile et al., 2022). This is because there

are several longitudinal data sets available. Longitudinal designs are useful for reaching more accurate findings on the causal linkages between HRM systems and performance outcomes than cross-sectional and time-lagged methods.

3. CONCLUSION

The strategic function of HRM in organisations has received a lot of attention during the past 30 years. The field's theoretical and empirical development has improved the rigor of scholarship and the caliber of conclusions that can be made. But a lot is still uncertain. The key theoretical frameworks, empirical findings, methodological issues, and current trends in strategic HRM research are hoped to be better understood by scholars with the aid of this review. Additionally, we believe that this publication will offer illuminating advice for future strategic HRM research. In the twenty-first century, strategic management of human capital will probably be a distinguishing characteristic of success, necessitating a greater emphasis on the ideologies, regulations, and procedures used to maximize SHRs. Strategic HRM is in a good position to contribute to this debate as long as the industry keeps posing and addressing worthwhile, strategic research topics.

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